

India-Bangladesh Connectivity: Implications for India's North East Development

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Connectivity is cornerstone to move forward greater bilateral cooperation and enhance trade, investment, people to people contracts and economic opportunities for India and Bangladesh. Both countries have all ingredient of transport connectivity as historical, cultural and political administrative familiarity and geographical proximity and both have been growing at 6 percent annually over the last two decades. But despite having these ingredients, India and Bangladesh are facing serious connectivity challenges both physical and non-physical that have limited the pace of economic growth and development and poor transportation infrastructure and connectivity impediments have limited the North Eastern Region of India and Bangladesh's opportunities to find markets for their products within and outside the region. This article discusses the rationale for connectivity between India and Bangladesh.

Keywords: Connectivity, transport, infrastructure, transit, and transportation cost, physical and non-physical barriers, comparative gain, Line of Credit

Introduction

India-Bangladesh connectivity has so far remained largely fragmented, even though the two neighbours were well connected by road, rail and waterways in the pre-partition era. These connections were operation till the 1965 War after which they were completely closed. Trade via waterways was resumed after the liberation of Bangladesh, but road and rail links were suspend between the two countries. Transit and connectivity issues have always been at the forefront in India-Bangladesh bilateral discussions (Selim, 2012: 100). After the liberation of Bangladesh, India took up the question of restoring these transit facilities with Bangladesh but it denied and restriction on movement of transit by road and rail continued. A protocol was signed between India and Bangladesh and transit only by inland water transport (IWT) was allowed (The Daily Star, March 20, 2013) There are existing transport and transit arrangements between India and Bangladesh in order to promote border trade with limits.

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Road Connectivity

Road transport plays the most important role in India-Bangladesh trade relations although this mode of communication is not cost effective. A significant proportion of freight and passenger traffic are carried by road. Petrapole (India) and Benapole (Bangladesh) border points are the two most important land ports for the overland trade between two countries. Nearly 70 to 80 per cent of bilateral overland trade passes through these ports (Selim, 2012: 100). This route is 5.5 metre wide and highly congested.

In the context of Nepal-Bangladesh, India has allowed a route (by road) between these two countries across the “Chicken’s Neck”¹ for bilateral trade, yet goods are required to be transhipped at Bangladesh border point. This route is more than 1300 km long and it is not very much cost effective, and consequently of very little use. Since this route cannot be used for third countries trade, Nepal’s export and import traffic uses Kolkata port, which is often congested compared to Bangladesh seaport of Mongla, which has spare capacity and a direct broad gauge link with Birgunj (Nepal) through Rauxal Indian border point. But for this route and Mongla port to be used for third country trade of Nepal, India has to agree to such transit (The Daily Star, February 24, 2010).

The road links between India and Bangladesh exist prior to liberation of Bangladesh but were not resumed after independence. There are three National Highways which connect India with Bangladesh. National Highway No. 35 extends from Kolkata to Barisal and Bongaon in India to Dhaka. National Highway No. 35 connects Barisal to Petrapole and National Highway No. 40 connects Siliguri and Guwahati in India to Chittagong and Dhaka via Comilla in Bangladesh. Moreover a number of state highways passing through Murshidabad, Balur Ghat and Haldibari connect India with Bangladesh (Thapliyal, 1999: 1921-22).

India’s Road Connectivity with Bangladesh, Bhutan and Nepal²

Asian Highway (AH) route AH-2 passes through Banglabandha-Siliguri-Kakarbhitta, near Siliguri. Further AH 48 extends from Thimphu-Phuentsholing-Border of India. In 2008, India has approved the proposal for amendment of AH routes proposed by the Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific of the United Nations (UNESCAP). The amendment to AH-2 includes inclusion of Phulbari between the route passing through Banglabandha and Siliguri and has defined the route of AH-2 at this location as ‘Banglabandha-Phulbari-Siliguri-Kakarbhitta’. The other amendment is providing link to Bhutan by extending route of AH 48 from Thimphu-Phuentsholing-Jaigon-Hasimara-Jailpaiguri-Phulbari and consequently connect with AH-2 at Phulbari in India. It is envisaged that this route would improve international trade among India, Bangladesh, Nepal and Bhutan and also provide connectivity to Thimphu with India through the Asian Highway route.

Rail Connectivity

India has the best railway system among the developing countries in the world. Railway played important role in integrating the Indian sub-continent during the British

period. Railway is the only mode which can play positive role in integrating South Asian region by allowing cross border movement of goods in bulk. However compared to highway connectivity of South Asia, railway network might require greater effort in view of gauge mismatch and multiple missing links between the countries. For example, India is having broad gauge all weather railways network whereas Bangladesh railway system is based mostly on meter gauge (De, 2013: 33).

During the pre-1947 period, railway was the most important mode of transportation. However, cross-border trade movement by rail has diminished or dwindled significantly today as a number of rail routes have become dormant. Only three broad gauge routes are operational now namely- Darsana-Gede, Rohanpur-Singhabad and Benapole-Petrapole. These corridors are used for export and import of goods (Selim, 2012: 100). Operation of Radhikapur-Birol route has remained suspended since 1 April 2007 due to broad gauging on the Indian side while the track on Birol-Parbatipur section in Bangladesh Railway is still in Metre Gauge. The Mahisasan-Shahbazpur MG route has not been in operation since December 1996 due to lack of traffic.³

Sl.No.	Rail Routes
1	Gede (India)-Darsana (Bangladesh)-Broad Gauge
2	Singhabad (India)-Rohanpur (Bangladesh)-Broad Gauge
3	Petrapole (India)-Benapole (Bangladesh)-Broad Gauge
4	Radhikapur (India)-Birol (Bangladesh)-Broad Gauge on Indian side and Metre Gauge on Bangladesh side
5	Mahisasan (India)-Shahbazpur (Bangladesh)-Metre Gauge

Source: <http://pib.nic.in/newsite/erelease.aspx?relid=31026>

India has been playing active role in linking Bhutan with India's railway networks; besides it is also helping Nepal in extending the railway line from Birgunj to inside the country. The restoration of India-Bangladesh railway link is most important (De, 2013: 33.) In this connection India and Bangladesh has restored India-Bangladesh friendship service train (the Moitri Train) on 14 April 2008, and the train has resume service between Kolkata and Dhaka. This is a progressive step towards fostering closer communication linkages between the two neighbouring countries which would facilitate movement of goods and people (Selim, 2012: 100). But this service so far is too much time consuming due to long delays in customs and immigration clearance. It takes nearly half a day to travel a distance of only 400 kilometres. Therefore in spite of a much fanfare launch this route is not very popular (Ibid).

Inland Water Transit

India and Bangladesh are the only two South Asian nation-states connected by inland water transport, which is the cheapest mode of transport. Before partition of India, trading items of North Eastern States of India used to move through the terri-

tory of East Pakistan, what is now Bangladesh. Even until 1965 (Indo-Pak war), transit through rail and Inland Water Transport were allowed (The daily Star, February 24, 2010). After the Liberation of Bangladesh, India and Bangladesh signed an Inland Water Transit and Trade Protocol in 1972 to ensure waterway transit for India through Bangladesh to the Northeastern states of India (Selim, 2012: 101). According to Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region, this protocol is mutually beneficial arrangement for the use of waterways for commerce and passage of goods between two places in one country through the territory of the other. The existing protocol routes are:

- Kolkata-Chandpur-Pandu-Silghat-Kolkata
- Kolkata-Chandpur-Karimganj-Kolkata
- Rajshahi-Dhulian-Rajshahi
- Silghat-Pandu-Ashuganj-Karimganj-Pandu-Silghat

Ports of Call

For inter-country trade, five ports of call have been designated by each country to provide facilities to the vessels of the other country. These are:

- India- Haldia (West Bengal), Kolkata (West Bengal), Pandu (Assam), Karimganj (Assam) and Shilghat (Assam).
- Bangladesh- Narayanganj, Khulna, Mongla, Sirajganj and Ashuganj.

Under this protocol, 50:50 cargos sharing by Indian and Bangladeshi vessels are permitted for both transit and inter-country trade.⁴

Connectivity of Northeastern Indian states to Bangladesh

North Eastern Region (NER) of India, comprising Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland and Tripura, shares almost 98 per cent of its land border with Bangladesh, Bhutan, China, Myanmar and Nepal (FICCI, 2012: 27). India and Bangladesh share 4096.70 km long international border, out of which 1880 km is with NER, which is about 46 per cent of India's border with Bangladesh, wherein 35 per cent is land border and more than 10 per cent is riverine tract. Four of northeastern states, namely Assam, Meghalaya, Tripura, and Mizoram, share international borders with Bangladesh. Except Meghalaya, the rest of the northeastern states share both land and riverine border with Bangladesh, among which Tripura and Mizoram have the longest land and riverine border with Bangladesh respectively. However, a large part of this international border with Bangladesh is porous (RIS, 2011: 30).

An assessment of Opportunity and constraints

The North Eastern Region is a reservoir of rich natural resources. Blessed with biodiversity, potential of huge hydro-power, oil gas, coal, limestone, forest wealth, fruits and vegetables, flowers, herbs and aromatic plants, rare and rich flora and fauna, the region has all the potential to transform itself into a commercial hub and tourist paradise.

The region is also a vibrant source of energy rich in oil, natural gas and India's

Table-2: NER-Bangladesh Border Length

State	Land border	Riverine	Total
Length in km			
Assam	160	103	263
Meghalaya	443	-	443
Tripura	773	83	856
Mizoram	58	260	318
Total	1434	446	1880

Source: RIS 2011: 31, Expansion of North East Trade with Bangladesh and Myanmar

largest perennial water system, the river Brahmaputra and its tributaries, which can be tapped for energy, irrigation and transportation. The valley of Brahmaputra river has fertile soil, which is a veritable storehouse of horticultural products and rare forest products (FICCI, 2012: 28).

Besides, NER is located at the door-step of East Asia region, with which India is increasing its economic ties and the region's geographical advantage provides a backdrop to its development as a base for cooperation with neighbouring countries such as Bangladesh, Bhutan and Nepal. But despite these advantages, NER has remains one of India's economically isolated and backward regions, which accounts for a mere 2 per cent of India's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2009-10 (RIS, 2011: 12).

North East Region is landlocked and is connected to the rest of India by 22 km wide stretch of land called the chicken neck. However, this route passes through hilly terrain with steep roads and multiple hairpin bands. Agartala is 1,650 km from Kolkata and 2,637 km from New Delhi via Shillong and Guwahati. But distance between Agartala and Kolkata via Bangladesh is just about 350 km. Moreover, on an average the distance between important cities of Bangladesh and Northeast India is 20-200 km (FICCI, 2012, p.28-29.). Moreover, Indian and Bangladesh waterways connect West Bengal and Assam (The Murung Express, June 12, 2014).

Map A: North East India and Bangladesh

India has been working with Bangladesh on bilateral projects to enhance connectivity and trade with the North East Region, and these projects at different levels started in June 2012. They are:

- *Inland Container Port at Ashuganj, Bangladesh:* During the visit of Sheikh Hasina, Prime Minister of Bangladesh, to India in January 2010, India and Bangladesh bilaterally agreed on inclusion of Ashuganj as a port of call in the Indo-Bangladesh Inland Water transit and trade Protocol. Under the protocol, inland vessels of one country can transit through the specified routes of the other country.
- *Widening of Ashuganj-Akhaura road in Bangladesh:* This project will provide connectivity to Northeastern state of Tripura.
- Under IWTT protocol it has been proposed to include additional sections from Rajshahi to Aricha and from Titas-Meghna junction to Akhaura.
- *Bridge over river Feni (at Sabroom, Tripura):* During the India-Bangladesh Joint Communiqué in January 2010, it has been decided to develop Sabroom-Ramgargh Land Custom Station (LCS) on Indo-Bangladesh border at Tripura. Sabroom is the existing LCS. In order to operationalise the two LCSs it has also been decided to construct bridge over Feni River which forms border between India and Bangladesh.
- Upgradation of infrastructure at Sutarkandi LCS to Integrated Check Post (ICP) in Assam.
- Border Haats at Balat and Kalaichar on the Meghalaya Border.
- Setting up of Integrated Check Post at Dawki (Dwaki-Tamabil).
- Upgradation the infrastructure of Land Custom Stations at Dalu, Borsora, and Ghasuapara.
- In Mizoram, ICP at Kawarpuchchiah/Demagiri-Thegamukh LCS.
- Use of Chittagong and Mongla ports in Bangladesh for Indian cargo.
- In Tripura, Development of ICP at Akhaura (Near Agartala).
- India announced grant to Bangladesh for construction of railway line between Akhaura and Agartala.⁵

During Sheikh Hasina's visit to India in January 2010, India and Bangladesh agreed to lay the railway track between Akhaura and Agartala. This railway link is 15.54 km, within which 5 km falls in Indian and the rest in Bangladesh. Sabroom is very close to India-Bangladesh border and nearly 70 km away from Chittagong Port. In other words, with the establishment of the new railway link, northeast India will be connected to the Chittagong International sea port by rail (BusinessLine, May 23, 2013).

On June 2014, India and Bangladesh have taken more pragmatic move in this regard and decided to start work early next year on a new rail link to ease surface transport. According to Chandra Pal, Joint Secretary of Railway Ministry: "With the setting up (of) new railway connectivity between India and Bangladesh, people of the two countries will benefit as they will come closer. Men and materials will be

ferried very smoothly.” He further said that, “The proposed rail link will not only improve bilateral ties but also help in establishing connectivity with inaccessible areas in the northeast as journey from Kolkata to Tripura and other northeastern states via Bangladesh will save cost, time and distance travelled” (Times of India, June 17, 2014).

Recently, India signed 22 agreements with Bangladesh and extended a New Line of Credit (LoC) of US\$ 2 billion to Bangladesh to develop infrastructure and also started two cross-border transport service between India and Bangladesh as Kolkata-Dhaka-Agartala and Dhaka-Shillong-Guwahati Bus Service and its Protocol was signed which would link West Bengal to three North Eastern States of India via Bangladesh’s Capital Dhaka.⁶ However, Bilateral Trade Agreement and Protocol on Inland Transit and Trade were renewed and Memorandum of Understanding to use Chittagong and Mongla Ports were signed.

India’s Northeastern states are surrounded by Bangladesh, Myanmar, Bhutan and China, so surface connectivity is an important factor for this eastern region of South Asia. The only land route to these states from within India is through Assam and West Bengal. But it passes through over hilly terrain with steep roads and multiple hairpin bends (Ibid).

Bangladesh has taken highly significant move at highest level in June 2014 and decided to allow India’s ferry food grain to the landlocked Northeastern states using its territory and infrastructure. Under a special transit facility, Bangladesh government has agreed to transport 10,000 tones of food grain for Tripura via its territory (The Murung Express, June 12, 2014). According to Tripura’s Food, Civil Supplies and Consumer Affairs Ministry: “Due to shortage of rail of rail wagons, inadequate storage facilities and various other bottleneck, the northeastern states have been suffering from poor supply of food grains for most part of the year, especially during the monsoon (June to September)”. Thus Bangladesh’s this initiative is very important for NER.

Rationale for Connectivity between India and Bangladesh

India’s strategy for asking transit from Bangladesh is just to connect a remote, neglected and discontented region to resource rich part of the country. It is in fact eyeing direct connectivity with Southeast Asia and China using the north-eastern states via Bangladesh. It is expected a lot from “Look East” policy which is “India’s effort to regionally integrate its economy with the fast growing East and Southeast Asian economies” (Haokip 2012: 390), so as to attract new investments, technology, employment and wealth creation to take place and therefore open up new markets in ASEAN for Indian goods, preferably manufactured in the North East region. It is further hoped that this natural resourceful area will attract domestic investment from the wider region (Murshid, 2011: 44). India’s long term goals depend on Myanmar. India-Myanmar engagement has been growing substantively, since early 1990s, with adoption of Look East Policy. Several studies show that Myanmar has been playing the lead catalytic role to facilitate economic integration between South and Southeast Asia. Myanmar is the land bridge that connects world’s two largest markets

South and Southeast Asia. In this way, Myanmar is an important country for two regions that helps integrate economies across the border (RIS, 2011: 50).⁷

If transit is allowed to Northeast India by Bangladesh, smaller North Eastern states like Tripura, Mizoram, Nagaland and Meghalaya can substantially reduce their travel time to India (Murshid, 2011: 44). For example, a 20-foot container takes at least 30-45 days to move between New Delhi and Dhaka through the maritime route (via Mumbai and Singapore/Colombo to Chittagong and then by rail to Dhaka, at a cost of around US\$2,500. If there were direct rail connectivity, the time would be reduced to 4-5 days and cost would drop to around US\$850 (Kharel, 2009: 5).

Access to Sea

NER is located geographically near to Chittagong port of Bangladesh. India is keenly interested in getting access to sea, particularly to this port for North Eastern States. It is possible that low density demand areas like Tripura, Manipur, Nagaland and Mizoram stand to benefit much through direct access to international markets at a much lower time and cost combination than currently enjoyed (Murshid, 2011: 44). For example, Agartala, the Capital of Tripura is only 75 km far from Chittagong. But goods from Agartala travel 1,645 km to Kolkata port through the “Chicken’s Neck”. Similarly, tea from Assam travels 1,400 km to reach Kolkata port. If there were transport cooperation between Indian and Bangladesh, goods would have travelled only around 400 km across Bangladesh to reach Kolkata (Kharel, 2009: 5). So the NER need Chittagong sea port for international and coastal trade. This transshipment is beneficial for Bangladesh but Bangladesh’s attitude toward NER’s transshipment facility has not been committal.

Comparative Advantage for India and Bangladesh

Bangladesh has its own interests in strengthening physical connectivity with India. Politically Bangladesh can use the transit as a leverage to settle some unresolved issues with India. Economically the country is likely to benefit from trade with Nepal and Bhutan. In this process, India has already allowed Bangladesh to conduct its trade with Nepal and Bhutan through its territory (Selim, 2012: 102). Moreover, a transit facility to India might open up new revenue for the country to import natural resources from the Northeast India and convert them into exportable commodities (Ibid).

A number of studies have shown the economic benefits that Bangladesh can harvest from granting transit connectivity to India:

Opportunities for Bangladesh

- Currently Bangladesh has large trade deficit with India. Bangladesh can reduce this trade deficit, trading in transport services with India. In this context, it is very important that transport services have no market elsewhere outside this sub-region and that these opportunities of trading in transport services may not continue for long. It is also important for sub-regional countries to recognise that no country other than Bangladesh can provide

these transport connectivity and services. Therefore, Bangladesh has huge opportunities of trading in transport services, and Bangladesh can emerge as a “transport hub” of a sub-region comprising Nepal, Bhutan and Northeast India. Consequently, this could develop win-win situation for all countries that are involved (Rahmatullah, 2009: 14).

- According to a study conducted by RIS (Research and Information System, New Delhi) in 2007, the transit revenue for Bangladesh was estimated between US\$ 660 million to US\$ 1060 million, and \$110 million to \$180 million respectively for the two different corridors.
- The markets of the North Eastern states would become more easily accessible for Bangladeshi products if transit is provided. Bangladesh can import raw material and export finished products to the northeast which would be cheaper due to the physical proximity.
- Transit to India could generate employment opportunities for Bangladeshi people. According to a 1999 estimate, transit to India would create 2.5 million jobs in Bangladesh in the transport sector and in the form of small business opportunities in the areas around the transit routes.
- Transit could lead to the development of transport sector in Bangladesh. For example, Bangladesh has fragile railway infrastructure which could be strengthened immensely. The extensive use of railways to facilitate smooth transit could bring the badly needed investment into Bangladesh railway infrastructure (Selim, 2012: 103).
- Murshid (2009) in his study recommended that railways should be the premier mode of transportation for India-Bangladesh transit. According to him rail transit is the most beneficial for Bangladesh. Although rail connectivity remains incomplete but there are a number of reasons that favour the rail option over the road. These are:
 - The Bangladeshi railway has turned into moribund organisation and over the years it has lost out to other modes of transport, especially roads. Bangladesh railways can tap into a large and profitable market due to potential demand of transit services. This is unique opportunity for Bangladesh to revive the railways and undertake a concerted effort to reclaim its share in the freight market.
 - Rail connectivity is a better option for Bangladesh than other transport because Bangladesh is densely populated and land scarce country. The basic rail infrastructure already exists and there is a need for improvement and upgradation which will not be land-intensive unlike roads.
 - Railways are much more environmental friendly and the cost of freight is much cheaper.
 - Bangladesh could earn enough revenue from Chittagong and Mongla sea

ports, if Bangladesh accords transit to India. Currently both seaports have excess capacity to handle additional cargoes and containers. For example, in Chittagong port 43 per cent of container and 46 per cent of cargo handling capacity remains unutilised. Bangladesh may earn an additional \$200 million annually by opening up its ports facilitation for handling Indian cargo (Selim, 2012: 103).

- The Chittagong port can become a modern busy port like Singapore and China serving the SAARC countries.
- Bangladesh may attract huge foreign investment and a throbbing service sector like Banks, insurance, hotels, rest houses, petrol pumps etc. and also may develop around the transcontinental roads and railways.
- The mutual transit will give Bangladesh a much shorter route to China and an initiative to link Chinese province of Yunan with Northeast of India, Myanmar, Thailand and Bangladesh (Dutta, 2010: 4).

Opportunities for India

There are following obvious opportunities for India if Bangladesh provides transit facility:

- India would be able to send goods to the north-east at much lower cost than that being incurred presently.
- It would help in attracting investment to the north-eastern region, both foreign and Indian, which is currently not taking place due to high transportation cost and absence of direct transit route through Bangladesh. Thus, one of the factors for the continued backwardness of the north-east would have been removed and states in the region would have been linked more closely with the mainland Indian economy. This would have had a salutary political effect.
- If Bangladesh provides their territories for transit, it would have also led to large scale investment of Chittagong and Mongla seaports in order to handle the additional volume from India, and the Nepalese and Bhutanese cargo.
- India would have facilitated large scale investment for the expansion and upgrading of transport infrastructure in Bangladesh.
- There would have been direct economic gain to Bangladesh by way of transit fee which, according to the most conservative estimates, would have amounted to at least \$1 billion per annum.
- If growth accelerates in the north-eastern states of India then Bangladesh's exports to these states would have increased substantially.
- Bangladesh's earnings from its exports to Nepal would also have increased sizably due to the transit facilities availability through India.

- In addition, Nepal's export earnings from Bangladesh and from destinations beyond Bangladesh would also have increased.
- India has granted transit facilities for trade between Bhutan and Bangladesh. This would have led to an increase in the two-way trade between these two countries (Dubey, 2013: 126).

Major connectivity challenges between India and Bangladesh

The surface transport network between India and Bangladesh still continues to remain fragmented due to various historical, political and economic reasons as well as lack of cooperation between both countries. As a result, their potential as engines of economic growth at the regional level remains unrealised. This is happening despite the fact that the basic infrastructure and facilities to establish mutually beneficial intra- and inter-regional transport linkages already exist in both the countries. The absence of such integration and continued non-cooperation in transport are having adverse impact on economic competitiveness of the two countries, and they are losing on many fronts (Rahmatullah, 2006: 4).

The most common concern amongst a fourth of Bangladeshi population is that transit to India might hamper Bangladesh's security. There is perception in Bangladeshi people that India could use transit facility to curb insurgency in its Northeastern states which could in turn threaten the security of Bangladesh. Moreover, transit to India could drag the country "into India's internal security matrix". Further some analysts consider that transit might spur arms and drugs trafficking through Bangladesh territory (Selim, 2012: 104). Due to all these security concern Bangladesh has been denying transit facility to India but Bangladesh has granted water transit to India which has not threatened the security of country.

There is another argument that the transit of Indian goods through its territory will overburden and even 'destroy' Bangladesh's transport infrastructure, i.e., railways, waterways, roads and highways. According to Saifur Rahman, the Finance Minister of Bangladesh, if Bangladesh provides transit facilities to India the country's entire road system will collapse (Dubey, 2013: 127).

In the context of road network, the major constraint is that Bangladesh roads have only two lanes and these were designed for an axle load of 8.2 tonnes. As such, heavily loaded Indian trucks cannot be allowed to ply on these roads, until expressways with higher loading standards are built along the national highways, which have average right of way (ROW) of around 40 metres or more. Progress with regard to widening major highway has also been very slow, including that of a four-lane Dhaka-Chittagong highway. In view of the above weakness of road sector, only small share of transit traffic can be carried by roads (Rahmatullah, 2013: 6).

In context of rail link, major constraints include weight restriction on Jamuna Bridge, where there is also a restriction on the number of trains that can cross the bridge per day. Other constraints include lack of rail connectivity with Northeast India, because Kulaura-Shahbazzpur/Mahishasan (39 km) rail link along with Akhaura-Kulaura-Karimganj route is yet to be recommissioned. A new rail link between Akhaura-Agartala (10 km) is still being built. In addition, Dhaka-Chittagong rail link

is also suffering from capacity constraints, as the progress in doubling the track is very slow. One more constraint is the lack of rail connectivity between Khulna and Mongla port, which is now included under Indian Line of credit (LOC) of US\$1 billion (Ibid).

With regard to inland water transport route, there is major constraint for movement of transit traffic between Kolkata and North East India because there is lack of transshipment port at Ashuganj. The project has now been included under Indian Line of Credit. In order to make this inland water transport route fully competitive, there is need to build an improve road link (35 km) between Ashuganj-Akhaura/Agartala (Ibid).

According to Abdullah (2011) there are some other major physical barriers including inadequate loop lengths, some missing links of shorter lengths in the border areas, lack of physical infrastructure at interchange points, load restrictions on bridge, lack of coordination for gauge conversion programmes on different railway systems and capacity constraints in certain sections of identified corridors. The railway management may not be able to implement the existing development projects in time on the one hand and operate international traffic on the other hand.

There are also some barriers in Bangladesh inland waterways including high rate, bank erosion, inadequate navigational aids and draft restriction of 1.83m, as well as poor coordination of jetties and piers and lack of sufficient storage space, cargo handling equipment and support craft. With regard to maritime transport, the major barriers are capacity constraints at many of the gateways, together with heavy siltation at channels where depths fluctuate with tide. Channel making are also not adequate and are poorly maintained, and cargo and ship handling equipment as well as floating craft are quite old in Mongla, Ashuganj and Chittagong ports.

India and Bangladesh are facing problems such as lack of agreements for smooth movement of freight and vehicles between the countries and those relating to delay in cargo clearance, facilitation or speed money payments, cumbersome transportation documents and customs procedures, etc.

Besides, some delays are associated with the preparation of customs documents and inspections due to lack of standardisation of documents and implementation of modern customs procedures (The Daily Star, September 21, 2011). For example, at the India-Bangladesh border, a consignment needs at least 17 documents, more than 330 signatures and a minimum of 67 copies at several stages for the final approval. Each country requires different documents, such as transit export and import declarations. Exports need separate documents on each side of the border, resulting in error. In the road sector, average time for a trade consignment to pass through the border is 4-6 days (De and Bhattacharyay, 2007:46).

Consequences of Poor Connectivity

Due to this poor regional connectivity between Bangladesh and the neighboring countries of India, Nepal and Bhutan, all the countries and their territories have been losing a great deal in many fronts. For example:

- The shipment of Assam tea to Europe is required to travel 1400 km to reach

Kolkata port through the “Chicken’s neck”, due to lack of agreement for India to use the traditional route through Chittagong port which would be shorter by more than 60 per cent in terms of distance.

- The southern border of Tripura State is only 75 km from Chittagong port, but goods from Agartala are required to travel 1645 km to reach Kolkata port through Siliguri in North Bengal. If transit facility is given by Bangladesh to India, goods will have travel only around 400 km across Bangladesh to reach Kolkata, and a much shorter distance to reach Chittagong port.
- India and Myanmar are jointly implementing “Kaladan Project” which connects the Sittwe port of Myanmar with Mizoram, partly through Kaladan River and partly by road. This is quite expensive alternative for India to have access to Northeast India via Kolkata port. This is an alternative to existing route through Lower Assam and West Bengal. If transport cooperation is provided by Bangladesh to India India could have used a much shorter route across Bangladesh (Rahmatullah, 2009:15).

These are major constraints in India-Bangladesh transport cooperation and also for their other neighbouring countries. In order to tackle these physical and non-physical problems various studies have been conducted to find out appropriate solution. These are:

Past initiative to address connectivity

The UN-ESCAP Initiative

UN-ESCAP took one of the pioneering efforts to establish regional connectivity through two of its famous projects, namely the Asian Highway (AH) and Trans Asian Railway (TAR) since 1959 and 1960 respectively. The AH Agreement has already been signed by 28 countries out of 32 and it came into force in July 4, 2005 (The Daily Star, March 28, 2011). India is also a party to this network. Asian highway passes through four states of North East India. It enters Meghalaya after crossing Bangladesh, and then enters Assam and pass through two more states, Nagaland and Manipur before entering Myanmar. This project is expected to promote trade, commerce and tourism in the region. It will provide a critical linkage between North-East India and South East Asian countries (Mandal, 2009:77). These are the two major routes which connect Southeast Asia and South Asia and Europe.

The Trans Asian Railway has been identified as Southern corridor from Indonesia via India to Turkey. It is of direct interest to South Asian countries and the route covers a distance of 35200 km, with five gauges involve, yet there are several missing links between Thailand-Myanmar, Myanmar-India and Pakistan (The Daily Star, March28, 2011).

In order to operationalise these networks, separate agreements are required to be signed by connected countries. Asian Highway network pass through India and Bangladesh territory and greater connectivity is important for both countries. Ini-

Map B: Asian Highway Route Map

tially, Bangladesh was not prepared to sign up AHN during Bangladesh National Party (BNP) period and wanted to change the route. But after the Awami League (AL) assumed the power in January 2009, the Cabinet approved Bangladesh's accession to the AHN in principle in a meeting held on 16 June 2009. Bangladesh foreign policy goals moved further and there is a proposal to build Dhaka-Yangon-Kunming road, which would allow transit connectivity to China from Chittagong port to eastern China. Moreover Bangladesh has a proposal for trilateral agreement on connectivity supported by China. These proposals are being propagated under the Kunming Initiative (BCIM) and therefore largely bypass India (Pattanayak, 2009: 3-4).

The SAARC Initiative

The SAARC summit was held in Islamabad in 2004 to decide the transport strength, transit and communication links among South Asian countries. This was followed by SAARC Regional Multimodal Transport Study (SRMTS) and which was completed in 2006. This study identified 10-road corridors, 5-Rail corridors, 2-inland water transport corridor, 10-Maritime and 16 Aviation Gateways for regional connectivity. SRMTS was approved during 14th SAARC Summit held in April 2007 in New Delhi. This summit also decided to extend SRMTS and include Afghanistan and develop a model regional transit and transport agreement (SRMTS, 2006: 1)

This study emphasis that integration of transport network of South Asia is especially crucial to countries such as Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh and Northeast India as this could serve to end their landlocked or semi-isolated status and could provide shorter transport and transit links. Nepal, Bhutan and North Eastern region of India within such a framework would have the benefit of improved access to Bangladesh's ports and could become important economic centre of region and choice of route and mode. In this respect improving connectivity by road, rail and inland water transport are especially important for eastern region of South Asia (SRMTS, 2006:2).

The Recent Development in India-Bangladesh Connectivity

There have been some positive developments on India-Bangladesh connectivity when the Awami League came into power with an absolute majority by the end of 2008. First, the Bangladeshi Prime Minister visited India in January 2010 and some decisions related to connectivity issues were taken at the end of visit. Secondly, an Asian Development Bank (ADB) study favours transit between the two countries. And, third there is another report which came out in April 2011 and this report states the official position of Bangladeshi government on this issue (Selim, 2012: 104).

Bangladeshi Prime Minister visit to India in 2010

India and Bangladesh made joint statement to strengthen connectivity. Bangladesh allowed India to use seaports, namely, Chittagong and Mongla. Both countries also identify some other areas of cooperation with regard to waterways and rail communication. Among other things, the two countries agreed to include Ashuganj and Silghat as the two new ports of call (Selim, 2012: 105). In 2007 India had requested Bangladesh to allow the use of the Ashuganj River port for the transportation of goods from Tripura because it is only 62 km away from Tripura (Pattanayak, 2009: 3).

The Asian Development Bank (ADB) Study Report

The Bangladeshi transport expert M. Rahmatullah conducted a study on transit in 2010 for Asian Development Bank (ADB). The study has quantified the benefit from transit to Bangladesh. According to report, Bangladesh would earn \$50 million per annum in the first five years. Further, the also study found the internal rate of return from transit is 33.46 per cent. It shows that trade in transport service is economically beneficial for Bangladesh. The study also identified probable profit making transit routes - seven road routes, six rail routes and two water routes (The Daily Star, April 21, 2011).

The Core Committee Study Report on Transit

The Bangladeshi Ministry of Commerce formed a core committee on transit on December 2, 2010. It was the very first initiative taken by Bangladesh government to evaluate the option of granting transit to India in economic terms. This committee was headed by Mozibur Rahman as the chairman of Tariff Commission, and it consisted of two sub-groups. Four issues have been dealt by the core committee. These are: probable transit routes, investment for infrastructure development and return from transit fee/charge, and economic impact of transit.

The core committee submitted its final report to Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina in January 2012. The report has identified seven road routes for transit traffic, six rail routes and tree new routes for inland water transport to facilitate transit (The Financial Express, February 6, 2012). Three of the seven probable land routes would give Bangladesh access to Bhutan and Nepal across Indian territory, and one of the six rail routes connects Bangladesh with Nepal (Table, 3).

Table-3: Core Transit Routes by Road, Rail and Inland Water Transport

S. No.	A-Road routes	
1	Kolkata-Petrapole/Benapole-Dhaka-Akhaura/Agartala	India & Bangladesh
2	Agartala-Akhaura-Chittagong	India & Bangladesh
3	Silchar-Sutarkandi-Chittagong Port	India & Bangladesh
4	Silchar-Sutarkandi-PaturiaFerry-Benapole-Kolkata	India & Bangladesh
5	SamdrupJonkhar (Bhutan)-Guwahati-Shillong-Tamabil-Sylhet-Chittagong	Bhutan, India & Bangladesh
6	Kathmandu-Kolkata/Phulbari-Banglabandha-Mongla/Chittagong	Nepal, India & Bangladesh
7	Thimpu-Phuentsholing-Jaigaon/Burrimari-Mongla/Chittagong	Bhutan, India & Bangladesh
	B-Rail routes	
8	Silchar-Mahisasan/Shahbazpur-DhakaICD-Banglabandha Bridge-Darshana-Kolkata	India & Bangladesh
9	Silchar-Mahisasan/Shahbazpur-Chittagong Port	India & Bangladesh
10	Agartala-Akhaura LCS-Dhaka ISD-Banglabandha-DarshanaBanglabandha-Darshana	India & Bangladesh
11	Agartala-Akhaura-Chittagong Port	India & Bangladesh
12	Kolkata-Petrapole/Benapole-Khulna-Mongla Port	India & Bangladesh
13	Birganj-Raxual-Katihari-Singabad/Rohanpur-Khulna-Mongla Port	Nepal & Bangladesh
	C-inland water transport route	
14	Kolkata-Ramongal-Mongla-Narayanganj-Ashuganj-by road to Agartala	India & Bangladesh

Source: *The Financial Express*, February 16, 2012 and *The Daily Star*, March 20, 2013.

The report, among other things, suggested charging a user fee instead of a transit fees for use on transit facilities. The report has recommended imposing user fee on various services as transportation and administrative services. For road transit, the user fees include cost of road damage, accident externalities, congestion cost and environment cost (Selim, 2012: 106). For example, report has proposed charges ranging between \$252 and \$511 for road routes to be imposed on each truck, coming from India, Bhutan and Nepal for using the Bangladesh territory (The Financial Express, February 6, 2012). The report firmly suggested for use of railway and waterways as the options for carrying the transit traffic, instead of road, due to poor condition (Ibid). For example, Bangladesh road network has structural weakness (as these were designed for 8.2 ton axle load and roads are only two lanes), these can be used in a

limited way to carry only high value commodities (The Daily Star, March 28, 2011).

The report also highlighted the detailed prospects of transit facilities through railway and waterways. It has made extensive economic analysis of transit, prospects of partnership with beneficiary countries, domestic responsibilities and related matters. Moreover legal requirements, operational aspects of transit and required protocols, standard operating procedures and institutional arrangement for transit operation (The Financial Express, February 6, 2012).

World Bank Initiative for Regional Transport Connectivity

On June 14, 2014 World Bank has approved 107 million credits for the Mizoram State Roads II- Regional Transport Connectivity project to improve connectivity of the landlocked state and help tap the potential of regional trade among neighbouring countries. The project will connect Mizoram and other Northeastern states road links with Bangladesh, as well as with Nepal, Bhutan and Myanmar (The Financial Express, June 15, 2014).

The road link will connect to Bangladesh and facilitate greater bilateral trade and access to Chittagong port, which is the nearest shipping port for the Northeastern region of India. The link will connect with Myanmar's border and facilitate connectivity with Myanmar and the rest of East Asia and beyond. Impact would be created by road link on trade and employment, within inter-state and between Mizoram and neighboring states. Being a distant hill state, connectivity is very important for Mizoram, which is geographically isolated from the mainland like the other north-eastern states. Long and difficult transportation routes over predominantly mountainous terrain have long hampered trade and development.

According to estimates, annual intra-regional trade in the region can be more than double from \$16 billion to \$38 billion annually, if trade barriers with neighbors were removed. Further, investments in transport infrastructure could reduce trade costs by more than 20 per cent in India and 12.5 per cent in Bangladesh.⁸

BBIN Transport Connectivity

Finally, in order to enhance connectivity, sub-regional framework BBIN-MVA (Bangladesh, Bhutan, India and Nepal-Motor Vehicle Agreement) was signed between the four SAARC countries for the regulation of passengers, personal and cargo vehicular traffic between these countries on June 15, 2015 in Thimphu, Bhutan. This agreement is beneficial for seamless mutual cross-border movement of passengers and goods for overall economic development of the region.

Conclusion

The analysis indicates that India and its close neighbouring countries - Bangladesh, Bhutan and Nepal, could gain considerably if transit connectivity is fully established by all modes and transit of goods or containers are allowed across North East India and Bangladesh. It could clearly be positive sum game for all. There is a need to provide transit by all countries to establish link with each other, on a reciprocal basis because the cost of non-cooperation transportation is very high in the region. India,

Nepal and Bhutan are asking for transit through Bangladesh as well as access to Bangladesh sea ports of Chittagong and Mongla. Recent joint communiqué issued by India and Bangladesh will open up connectivity sub-regionally to these countries. In this process Bangladesh could gain considerably through in trading in transport services with the land locked countries.

However, economies of North East India and Bangladesh are complementary, and accessibility of North East India to Chittagong port could open up their economy to outside the world. Bangladesh has scarcity of mineral resources which has been major problem for the development of the country. Other hand Northeast India has huge mineral resource base which can fill up Bangladesh's vacuum. Moreover, their forest resource base and hydro-power potentials can be of great help for the development of Bangladesh. Political commitment is must for establishing regional transport connectivity. In this context India-Bangladesh joint communiqué is very important and it is a marker of dramatically improved relations between India and Bangladesh.

Notes

¹ "Chicken's Neck" is also known as Siliguri Corridor, and is a narrow stretch of Indian territory in northern West Bengal that connects India's Northeastern states to the rest of India, with the countries such as Nepal and Bangladesh lying on either side of the corridor, and Bhutan lies on the north side of it.

²<http://www.pib.nic.in/newsite/erelease.aspx?relid=36037>

³<http://pib.nic.in/newsite/erelease.aspx?relid=31026>

⁴<http://mdoner.gov.in/content/inland-waterways-ner>

⁵ <http://mdoner.gov.in/content/bangladesh>

⁶ <http://pib.nic.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx>

⁷ For details about the evolution of India's Look East Policy and its approaches, read (Haokip 2011).

⁸ <http://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2014/06/12/107-million-world-bank-project-to-connect-mizoram-with-bangladesh-and-myanmar-via-roads>

References

- Abdullah, M. M. (2011, September 21). *Regional Connectivity: Problems and Prospects*, *The Daily Star*. Retrieved April 26, 2014, from <http://archive.thedailystar.net/newDesign/news-details.php?nid=203266>
- Abdullah, M. M. (2011). *Transit and Connectivity: Regional Approach*, *The Daily Star*. Retrieved June 17, 2014, from <http://archive.thedailystar.net/suppliments/2011/anniversary/part5/pg9.htm>
- Acharya, Loknath and Ashima Marwaha. (2012). *Status Paper on India-Bangladesh Economic Relations*. New Delhi: FICCI.
- Ahsan, N. (2012, February 16). *Core committee proposes specific transit charges for road routes*, *The Financial Express*. Retrieved June 12, 2014, from http://www.thefinancialexpress-bd.com/old/more.php?news_id=120302&date=2012-02-16

- BusinessLine. (2013, March 24). *Agartala-Akhaura rail link work to start soon*. Retrieved June 17, 2014, from <http://www.thehindubusinessline.com/industry-and-economy/logistics/agartalaakhaura-rail-link-work-to-start-soon/article4746165.ece>
- Byron, R. K. (2011, April 21). *Transit raises hope for robust earnings*. Retrieved June 10, 2014, from <http://archive.thedailystar.net/newDesign/news-details.php?nid=182449>
- De, Prabir. (2011, December). Why is trade at border a costly affair in South Asia? An empirical investigation. *Contemporary South Asia*, 19(4), 441-464.
- De, Prabir. (2013). *Connectivity, Trade Facilitation and regional Cooperation in South Asia*. New Delhi: Commonwealth Secretariat.
- De, Prabir and Biswa N. Bhattacharyay. (2007). *Deepening India-Bangladesh Economic Cooperation: Challenges and Opportunities. RIS Discussion Paper no.130*. New Delhi: Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS).
- Dubey, M. (2013). *India's Foreign Policy Coping with the Changing World*. New Delhi: Pearson Publication.
- Dutta, P. (2010). *India-Bangladesh Relations: Issues, Problems and Recent development*. New Delhi: Institute of Peace and Conflict Studies (IPCS).
- Dutta, S. (2012). *India-Bangladesh Cross-border Connectivity*. In S. S. Pattanaik, *Four Decades of India-Bangladesh Relations: Historical Imperative and Future Direction*. New Delhi: Gyan Publication.
- Haokip, T. (2012). Recent trends in regional integration and the Indian experience. *International Area Studies Review* 15(4) 377– 392.
- Haokip, T. (2011). India's Look East Policy: Its Evolution and Approach. *South Asian Survey* 18(2) 239–257.
- Kharel, P. (2009). South Asian transit arrangement. *SAWTEE Briefing Paper* (11).
- Mandal, R. K. (2009, January-March). Emerging Scenario of Trade Potentialities of North-East India: Challenges and Opportunities. *Journal of Global Economy*, 5(1), 68-89.
- Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region, North East India. (n.d.). *Indo-Bangladesh Protocol on Inland Water Transit & Trade*. Retrieved June 7, 2014, from <http://mdoner.gov.in/content/indo-bangladesh-protocol-inland-water-transit-trade#intro>
- Ministry of Development of north Eastern Region, North East India. (n.d.). *Bilateral Projects with Bangladesh & Indian Projects to Promote Connectivity & trade with NER*. Retrieved June 18, 2014, from <http://mdoner.gov.in/content/bangladesh>
- Murshid, K. (2011, April 23). Transit and Trans-shipment: Strategic Considerations for Bangladesh and India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, XLVI(17), 43-51.
- Pattanaik, S. S. (2009, August). India, Bangladesh and southeast Asia Connecting the Neighborhood. *IPCS Issue Brief*(113), 1-4.
- Press Information Bureau, Government of India. (2007, September). *Rail Link with Bangladesh*. Retrieved June 15, 2014, from <http://pib.nic.in/newsite/erelease.aspx?relid=31026>

- Press Information Bureau, Government of India. (2008, March 5). *Road Connectivity with Nepal, Bhutan and Bangladesh*. Retrieved June 12, 2014, from <http://www.pib.nic.in/newsite/erelease.aspx?relid=36037>
- Rahmatullah, M. (2006). *Transport Issue & Integration In South Asia*. Bangkok: UN-ESCAP.
- Rahmatullah, M. (2009, December). *Regional Connectivity: Opportunities for Bangladesh to be a Transit Hub*. *Journal of Bangladesh Institute of Planners*, 2, 13-29.
- Rahmatullah, M. (2010, February 2). *Regional Connectivity Indo-Bangladesh initiative*, *The Daily Star*. Retrieved April 26, 2014, from <http://archive.thedailystar.net/suppliments/2010/02/ds19/segment2/initiative.html>
- Rahmatullah, M. (2011). *Connectivity issue: Political leaders set the tone*, *The Daily Star*. Retrieved March 7, 2014, from <http://archive.thedailystar.net/suppliments/2011/anniversary/part5/pg8.htm>
- Rahmatullah, M. (2013, March 20). *Regional Transport Connectivity Its current state*, *The Daily Star*. Retrieved February 28, 2014, from <http://archive.thedailystar.net/beta2/news/its-current-state/>
- RIS. (2011). *Expansion of North East India's Trade and Investment within Bangladesh and Myanmar: An assessment of the opportunities and Constraints*. New Delhi: Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS).
- SAARC Secretariat. (2006). *SAARC Regional Multimodal Transport Study (SRMTS)*. Kathmandu.
- Sanyal, S. (2012, July 30). *Bilateral water transport deal favours Bangladesh*, *BusinessLine*. Retrieved April 26, 2014, from <http://www.thehindubusinessline.com/opinion/bilateral-water-transport-deal-favours-bangladesh/article3704043.ece>
- Selim, I. (2012). *Bangladesh-India Connectivity: A focus on Transit*. In S. S. Pattanaik, *Four Decades of India-Bangladesh Relation: Historical Imperative and Future direction*. New Delhi: Gyan Publication.
- Subramanian, Uma and John Arnold. (2001). *Forging Subregional Links in Transportation and Logistics in South Asia*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank.
- Taneja, et al. (2013). *India's Role in Facilitating Trade under SAFTA. Working Paper No. 263*. New Delhi: Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations.
- The Financial Express. (2014, June 15). *World Bank credit for Mizoram road with Bangladesh, Nepal*. Retrieved June 17, 2014, from <http://www.thefinancialexpress-bd.com/2014/06/15/39586>
- The Murung Express. (2014, June 12). *Bangladesh allows transit of foodgrains to NE*. Retrieved June 19, 2014, from <http://www.morungexpress.com/regional/116924.html>
- Times of India. (2014, June 17). *Work on India-Bangladesh railway link from 2015*. Retrieved June 19, 2014, from <http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/India/Work-on-new-India-Bangladesh-railway-link-from-2015/articleshow/36725087.cms>